

$(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g$ closed sets in Bitopological spaces

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to introduced the new type of closed sets called $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g$ closed set. We introduce and study a new class of spaces namely $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g T_{1/2}$ space and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g T_{3/4}$ space. Also we find some basic properties and applications of $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g$ closed sets.

Keywords: $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g$ open; $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g$ closed; $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g T_{1/2}$ space and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g T_{3/4}$ space.

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1. Introduction

Closed sets are fundamental objects in a topological space. For example one can define the topology on a set by using either the axioms for the closed sets or the Kuratowski closure axioms. In 1971, Levine [7] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets in topological spaces. Also he introduced the notion of semi open sets in topological spaces. Bhattacharyya and Lahiri introduced a class of sets called semi generalized closed sets by means of semi open sets of Levine and obtained various topological properties.

The notion of Q^* - closed sets in a topological space was introduced by Murugalingam and Lalitha [9] in 2010 . In the year 2012, P. Padma introduced the concept of $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - Q^*$ closed sets in bitopological spaces . Also she introduced the notion of $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - Q^*$ continuous maps in bitopological spaces.

The aim of this paper is to introduced the new type of closed sets called $Q^* g$ closed. We introduce and study a new class of spaces namely $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g T_{1/2}$ space and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g T_{3/4}$ space. Also we find some basic properties and applications of $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* g$ closed sets.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper X and Y always represent nonempty bitopological spaces (X, τ_1, τ_2) and (Y, σ_1, σ_2) . For a subset A of X , $\tau_1 - cl(A)$, $\tau_1 - Q^* cl(A)$ (resp. $\tau_1 - int(A)$, $\tau_1 - Q^* int(A)$) represents closure of A and Q^* closure of A (resp. interior of A , Q^* - interior of A) with respect to the topology τ_1 . We shall now require the following known definitions.

Definition 2.1 - A subset S of X is called $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - open if $S \in \tau_1 \cup \tau_2$ and the complement of $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - open set is $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - closed.

Example 2.1 - Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, $\tau_1 = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ a, b \} \}$ and $\tau_2 = \{ \phi, X, \{ b \} \}$.

Then τ_1 - open sets on X are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}$ and τ_2 - open sets on X are $\phi, X, \{b\}$. Therefore, $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - open sets on X are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$ and $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - closed sets are $X, \phi, \{b, c\}, \{c, a\}, \{c\}$.

Definition 2.3 - A subset A of a bitopological space (X, τ_1, τ_2) is called $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - semi generalized closed (briefly $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - sg closed) set if and only if $\tau_1 \tau_2 - scl(S) \subseteq F$ whenever $S \subseteq F$ and F is $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - semi open set. The complement of $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - semi generalized closed set is $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - semi generalized open.

Definition 2.4 - A subset A of a bitopological space (X, τ_1, τ_2) is called $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - generalized closed (briefly $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - g closed) set if and only if $\tau_1 \tau_2 - cl(S) \subseteq F$ whenever $S \subseteq F$ and F is $\tau_1 \tau_2$ - open set. The complement of $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - generalized closed set is $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - generalized open.

Definition 2.5 - A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called a Q^* **generalized closed** set (briefly Q^* **g - closed**) if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is Q^* open in (X, τ) . The complement of a Q^* g - closed set is called a Q^* **g - open** set.

3. Q^* g closed

In this section we introduce a new type of closed set called Q^* g closed.

Definition 3.1 - A subset A of a bitopological space (X, τ_1, τ_2) is called a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* **generalized closed** set (briefly $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* **g closed**) if $\tau_i \tau_j - cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\tau_i \tau_j$ - Q^* open in (X, τ_1, τ_2) , where $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$. The complement of a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g - closed set is called a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* **g - open** set.

Example 3.1 : Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau_1 = \{\phi, X\}$, $\tau_2 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$ then $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, a\}$ and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open sets are $\phi, X, \{a, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{c\}, \{a\}, \{b\}$.

Theorem 3.1 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - semi closed.

Remark 3.1 : The converse of the above theorem need not be true. The following example supports our claim.

Example 3.2 : Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{\phi, X\}$ then $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, a\}$. Here $\{a, b\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - semi closed but not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Theorem 3.2 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open.

Remark 3.2 : The converse of the above theorem is not true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.3 : In example 3.2, $\{a\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g - open set but not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open.

Theorem 3.3 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proof : Let A be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* closed set. Then $X - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open. We have to show that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed. Since every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open, we have $X - A$ is

$(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open . Thus , A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Remark 3.3 : The converse of the above theorem is not true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.4 : In example , $\{ b , c \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set but not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* closed.

Theorem 3.4 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Proof : Let A be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set and U be any $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open set containing A in X . We have to show that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed . Since every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open and A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open in X . Hence X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Remark 3.4 : The converse of the above theorem is true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.5 : Let $X = \{ a , b , c \}$, $\tau_1 = \{ \phi , X \}$, $\tau_2 = \{ \phi , X , \{ c \} , \{ a , c \} \}$ then $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed sets and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets are $\phi , X , \{ b \} , \{ a , b \} , \{ b , c \}$.

Theorem 3.5 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - αg^{**} closed.

Proof : Let A be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set such that $A \subseteq U$, where U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open . We have to show that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - αg^{**} closed . Since every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - α closed and A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \alpha \text{cl} (A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g^{**} open in X . Hence A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - αg^{**} closed.

Remark 3.5 : The converse of the above theorem is true .

Example 3.6 : In example 3.1 , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - αg^{**} closed and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets are $\phi , X , \{ b \} , \{ c \} , \{ a , b \} , \{ b , c \} , \{ c , a \}$.

Theorem 3.6 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open.

Proof : Let S be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open set in X . Then $X - S$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed.

Claim : S is a $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - Q^* g open set . i.e) to prove $X - S$ is a $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - Q^* g closed set . i.e) to prove $\tau_1 \tau_2 - \text{cl} (X - S) \subseteq F$ whenever $X - S \subseteq F$, F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open . Let $X - S \subseteq F$ and F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open . Since $X - S$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed , we have $\tau_1 \tau_2 - \text{cl} (X - S) = X - S \subseteq F$.

$\Rightarrow X - S$ is a $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - Q^* g closed set.

Thus , S is a $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - Q^* g open set.

Theorem 3.7 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proof : Let A be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set. Then $X - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open . We have to show that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed . Since every open set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open , we have $X - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open. Thus,

A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Remark 3.6 : The converse of the above theorem is not true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.7 : In example 3.1 , $\{ a , b \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed but not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X.

Note 3.1 : The family of all $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed subsets of a bitopological space X is denoted by $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g.

Proposition 3.1 : If $A, B \in (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g then $A \cup B \in (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g.

Proof : Let A and B be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets in X.

Claim : $A \cup B$ be a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets in X . i.e) to prove $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A \cup B) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \cup B \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X . Since, A and B be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets in X we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X and $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (B) \subseteq U$ whenever $B \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X. Since X be a bitopological space , we have finite union of closed sets are closed.

$\Rightarrow \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A \cup B) \subseteq U$ whenever $(A \cup B) \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X.

$\Rightarrow A \cup B$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets in X .

$\Rightarrow A \cup B \in (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g.

Remark 3.7 : The intersection of 2 $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets are $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed . The following example supports our claim.

Example 3.8 : In example 3.2 , $\{ b , c \}$ and $\{ c \}$ are $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set . $\{ b , c \} \cap \{ c \} = \{ c \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Remark 3.8 : The union of 2 $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed sets are $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed . The following example supports our claim.

Example 3.10 : In example 3.1 , $\{ c , a \}$ and $\{ c \}$ are $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set . $\{ c , a \} \cup \{ c \} = \{ a , c \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Theorem 3.8 : The intersection of a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed and a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed set is always $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proof : Let A be a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed and let F be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed . If U is an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open set with $A \cap F \subseteq U$ then $A \subseteq U \cup F^c$ and so $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \subseteq U \cup F^c$. Now $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A \cap F) \subseteq \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \cap F \subseteq U$. Hence $A \cap F$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Example 3.11 : In example 3.2 , $\{ b \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed and $\{ a , b \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed . $\{ b \} \cap \{ a , b \} = \{ b \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proposition 3.2 : If A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed subset of X then A is an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* closed subset of X .

Proof : Since A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed, $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$. Hence A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Remark 3.9 : The following example supports our claim.

Example 3.12 : In example 3.1, $\{a, c\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g open and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed. Then $\{a, c\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Theorem 3.9 : If A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set in X then A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed if and only if $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Proof : Necessity : Let A be a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set.

Claim : $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g - closed . ie) To prove $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A = \phi$. Since A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed, we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) = A$. ie) $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A = \phi$. Hence $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g - closed.

Sufficiency : Let $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A$ be a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g - closed set.

Claim : A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed . ie) To prove $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) = A$. Since, $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

$\Rightarrow \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) - A = \phi$. Also A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed. Therefore, A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed.

Proposition 3.3 : If A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed subset of X then A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proof : Let A be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X .

Claim : A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed. ie., to prove $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X . Let $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X . Since A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X , we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) = A$

Since $A \subseteq U$, we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) = A \subseteq U$. Therefore, A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Remark 3.10 : But the converse of the above proposition is not true in general. It is shown in the example 3.1. The subset $\{b\}$ of a bitopological space X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed but it is not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X .

Proposition 3.4 : If A is a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set of X such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A)$ then B is also an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set of Y .

Proof : Let A be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set of X such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A)$.

Claim : B is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set of X . ie) to prove $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(B) \subseteq U$ whenever $B \subseteq U$ & U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X . Let $B \subseteq U$ & U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in Y . Since A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed in X , we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ & U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open in X . Since A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X , we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) = A$. Since $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A)$, we have B is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X & $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(B) = B$. Since B

$\subseteq U$ we have B is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Remark 3.11 : The following example show that $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closeness is independent from $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - \hat{g} closeness , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closeness , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $g\alpha$ closeness and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - α closeness.

Example 3.11 : In example 3.1 , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $\{ a, b \}$ is Q^* g closed but neither $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - \hat{g} closed , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closed and the set $\{ a, c \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed but neither $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $g\alpha$ closed and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - α closed.

Theorem 3.10 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closed.

Proof : Let A be an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Claim : A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closed . Since every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - semi closed and A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed we have $\tau_i \tau_j$ - scl (A) $\subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ & U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open in X . Hence A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closed.

Remark 3.12 : The following example shows that converse of the above theorem need not be true.

Example 3.12 : In example 3.2 , $\{ a \}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closed but not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Theorem 3.11 : A subset S of X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed if and only if $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - cl (S) – S contains no non - empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set.

Proof:

Necessity : Suppose that S is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Claim : $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - cl (S) – S contains no non - empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set . Assume the contrary . Let F be a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - semi closed set such that $F \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - cl (S) – S .

Since $F \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - cl (S) – S , we have $F \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - cl (S) \cap ($X - S$).

$$\Rightarrow F \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl} (S) \text{ and } F \subseteq X - S \dots\dots\dots (3 . 1) .$$

Since F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed , we have $X - F$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open in X . Since $F \subseteq X - S$, we have $S \subseteq X - F$. Therefore , $S \subseteq X - F$ and $X - F$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open.

By the definition of $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set , it follows that

$$(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl} (S) \subseteq X - F .$$

$$\Rightarrow F \subseteq X - ((\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl} (S)) \dots\dots\dots (3 . 2) .$$

From (3 . 1) and (3 . 2) , we have

$$F \subseteq [(\tau_i , \tau_j)^* - \text{cl} (S)] \cap [X - (\tau_i , \tau_j)^* - \text{cl} (S)] = \phi .$$

Therefore, $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ contains no non - empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ set.

Sufficiency : Suppose that $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ contains no non empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ set.

Claim : S is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$. i.e) to prove $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \subseteq G$ whenever $S \subseteq G$ and G is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{open}$ in X . Let $S \subseteq G$ and G is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{open}$ in X . If $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \not\subseteq G$, we have $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \subseteq X - G$ and $((\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S)) \cap (X - G) \neq \phi$.

Since $S \subseteq G$, we have $X - G \subseteq X - S$.

$$\Rightarrow (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \cap (X - G) \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \cap (X - S).$$

$$\Rightarrow (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \cap (X - G) \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S.$$

Since G is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{open}$, we have $X - G$ is a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ set . Therefore , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) \cap (X - G)$ is a non - empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ set . This is a contradiction to our assumption that $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ contains no non - empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ set . Therefore , S is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$.

Corollary 3.1 : Let S be $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$ set in X . Then S is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ if and only if $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ is $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - \text{closed}$.

Proof :

Necessity : Let S be a $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$ set in X . Suppose that S is $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - \text{closed}$.

Claim : $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$. Since S is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$, we have $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) = S$. $\Rightarrow (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S = \phi$. Therefore , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$.

Sufficiency : Suppose that $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$.

Claim : S is $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - \text{closed}$. Since S be $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$ set in X and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$. Then $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S$ be does not contain any non empty $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ subset.

$$\Rightarrow (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) - S = \phi.$$

Thus , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(S) = S$. Therefore , S is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed}$ in X .

Proposition 3.5 : Let $A \subseteq Y \subseteq X$ and suppose that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$ in X . Then A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{g closed}$ relative to Y .

Proof : Let $A \subseteq Y \subseteq X$. Suppose that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - Q^* \text{g closed}$ in X .

Claim : A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{g closed}$ relative to Y .

i.e) to prove $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{open}$ in Y . Let $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{open}$ in Y .

Since , A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed in X we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\tau_i \tau_j$ - open in X.

Since $A \subseteq Y \subseteq X$, we have A is $\tau_i \tau_j$ - closed in Y and $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) = A$. Since $A \subseteq U$ we have A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed in Y.

Theorem 3.12 : In (X , τ_1 , τ_2) , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gO (X) = (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gC (X)$ if and only if every subset of X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proof :

Sufficiency : Suppose that $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gO (X) = (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gC (X)$. Let A be a subset of X.

Claim : A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

i.e) to prove $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \subseteq F$ whenever $A \subseteq F$ and F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open . Since every Q^* open set is open and let $A \subseteq F$ and F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open . Since $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $Q^*O (X) = (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $Q^*C (X)$, we have F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X . Since $A \subseteq F$, we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (A) \subseteq \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (F) = F$. Thus A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Necessity : Suppose that A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Claim : $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gO (X) = (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gC (X)$. Let F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g open in X . Since A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed , F is $(\tau_1, \tau_2)^*$ - Q^* g closed .

$$\Rightarrow \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (F) \subseteq F.$$

$$\Rightarrow \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl} (F) = F.$$

Therefore , F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X.

Let G is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed in X . Then $X - G$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open . Since $X - G$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed , we have $X - G$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed in X . $\Rightarrow G$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g open in X.

Therefore , $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gO (X) = (\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - $gC (X)$.

Remark 3.12 : The following diagram shows the relationships of Q^* g closed sets with known existing sets . $A \rightarrow B$ represents A implies B but not conversely.

Proposition 3.6 : If A is both $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g open and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed, then A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Proof : Let A be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g open and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed.

Claim : A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

ie) to prove $\tau_i \tau_j - cl(A) = A$. Obviously $A \subseteq A$ and A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g open. Since, A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed, we have $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - cl(A) \subseteq A$. Also $A \subseteq (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - cl(A)$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - cl(A) = A \\ &\Rightarrow A \text{ is } (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{closed.} \\ &\Rightarrow A \text{ is } (\tau_i, \tau_j)^* - \text{g closed in } X. \end{aligned}$$

4. Applications :

We introduce the following definitions

Definition 4.1 : A space X is called a

- i. $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g $T_{1/2}$ space if every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed
- ii. $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g $T_{3/4}$ space if every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed
- iii. $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g T_S space if every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - semi closed
- iv. $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g T_{sg} space if every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - sg closed
- v. $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g T_C space if every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed

Proposition 4.1 : A bitopological space X is an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g $T_{1/2}$ - space if and only if $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed for each $x \in X$.

Proof : Suppose that X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g $T_{1/2}$ and for each $x \in X$, $\{x\}$ is not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed. Since X is the only $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g open set containing $\{x\}^c$, $\{x\}^c$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed and thus $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* closed. Hence $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open.

Conversely, assume that $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed for each $x \in X$.

Claim : X is an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g $T_{1/2}$ space. i.e) to prove that, every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed. By assumption, $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed for any $x \in X$. $\Rightarrow \{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed for any $x \in \tau_i \tau_j - cl(F)$.

Case (i) Suppose $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open. Since F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q* g closed set, we have $\{x\} \cap F \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, $x \in X \Rightarrow F$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed.

Case (ii) Suppose $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed . If $x \notin F$ then $\{x\} \subseteq \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(F) - F$ which is a contradiction . Therefore , $x \in F$. $\Rightarrow F$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed. Thus in both cases, we conclude that F is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - closed. Hence , X is an $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{1/2}$ space.

Lemma 4.1 : In any space a singleton is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open if and only if it is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open.

Theorem 4.1 : For a bitopological space X , the following conditions are equivalent

- i) X is a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{3/4}$ space
- ii) Every singleton $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.
- iii) Every singleton $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed.

Proof :

i) \Rightarrow ii) : If $\{x\}$ is not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed then $X / \{x\}$ is not $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g open & thus $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed . By i) , $X / \{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ -g closed . ie) $\{x\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open.

ii) \Rightarrow i) : Let $A \subseteq X$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed . Let $x \in \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A)$.

We consider the following two cases :

Case i) : Let $\{x\}$ be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* open . Since x belongs to the $\tau_i \tau_j$ - closure of A then $\{x\} \cap A \neq \emptyset$. This shows that $x \in A$.

Case ii) : Let $\{x\}$ be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed . If we assume that $x \notin A$, then we would have

$x \in \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) / A$, which cannot happen according to lemma 4.1 . Hence $x \in A$.

So in both cases we have $\tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A) \subseteq A$. Since the reverse inclusion is trivial , then

$A = \tau_i \tau_j - \text{cl}(A)$ or equivalently A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

ii) \Rightarrow iii) Follows from lemma 4.1 .

Theorem 4.2 : Every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{1/2}$ space is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{3/4}$ space.

Remark 4.1 : The converse of the above theorem is true in general . The following example supports our claim .

Example 4.1 : In example 3.1 , X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{3/4}$ space and $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{1/2}$ space.

Theorem 4.3 : In a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{3/4}$ space , every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Proof : Let X be a $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{3/4}$ space . Let A be $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set of X . We know that every $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed set is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed . Since X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{3/4}$ space , A is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - g closed.

Theorem 4.4 : If X is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{1/2}$ space with $Y \subseteq X$, then Y is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g $T_{1/2}$ space.

Proof : For $y \in Y$, $\{y\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed in X . Using proposition 4.1 , $\{y\}$ is $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - open or $(\tau_i, \tau_j)^*$ - Q^* g closed in Y .

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